

Epoxidation reactions of some selected olefins catalyzed by iron complexes

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Epoxidation of some simple and common olefin substrates catalyzed by different iron complexes reported in recent literature are briefly discussed in this mini review. Comparative yields by different iron complexes are highlighted.

Keywords: Iron, catalysis, epoxidation, alkenes.

Introduction

The word catalyst was introduced into science by the great Swedish chemist Jons Jakob Berzelius in 1835¹. The process by which a substance speeds up a chemical reaction without being consumed or altered in the process is known as catalysis. Substances that can accomplish this remarkable deed are designated as catalysts and are of great importance in chemistry and biology. The use of proper catalyst in any particular reaction not only saves time but also saves energy, gives anticipated product more easily in effective way and finally attractive from both economic and environmental standpoints. An epoxide is a cyclic ether with a 3-membered ring. This approximates an equilateral triangle which makes it strained and hence highly reactive than other ethers. Over the past few decades epoxidation reactions are of great interest since they lead to valuable and versatile intermediates for development of pharmaceutically active compounds²⁻⁴, polymers and paints⁵⁻⁷ among others. Many epoxides are generated by treating olefins with peroxide containing reagents, which donate a single oxygen atom. Among the various oxidants, hydrogen peroxide is one of the most practical reagents (second only to air) in terms of cost and atom efficiency. Uncatalyzed epoxidation of alkenes with peroxy-carboxylic acids is a fundamental reaction in organic chemistry that is commercially exploited to epoxidize internal alkenes of fatty acids. Peracetic acid is capable of epoxidizing more electron deficient terminal alkenes, albeit at elevated temperatures and with long reaction times that

significantly reduce the selectivity of the reaction⁸. The selection of a practical and effective oxidant has been welcomed as a means of achieving environmentally benign and high-yield epoxidation. Metal-catalyzed oxygenation of organic substrates is becoming an increasingly important area in modern organic synthesis due to better prospect⁹⁻¹⁶. The development of catalytic epoxidation agents that are rapid, selective, scalable and inexpensive with a wide substrate scope remains an important goal. Epoxidations are mainly catalyzed by the transition metal compounds of molybdenum, ruthenium, rhodium, palladium and iridium complexes have been developed that can dramatically enhance the selectivity and the rate of epoxidation of olefins¹⁷⁻²¹. But the limited availability of these metals as well as their high prices and significant toxicity makes it desirable to search for clean, sustainable and environmentally friendly alternatives. So, chemists are concentrating their attention on the use of 3d metal compounds because of their own remarkable advantages and unique features²²⁻²⁶. In this effort iron compounds are important for catalyzing these epoxidation reactions because iron is abundant (~4.7 wt % in the earth's crust), cheap, relatively non-toxic in comparison to other metals, benign, shows variable oxidation states (from -II to +VI) and is very willing to ligation with nitrogen-, oxygen- or phosphorous-based ligand sets. Iron may be considered as a member of both early and late first transition series. Iron ion can bind with both hard and moderately soft donor sites. Many iron salts and iron complexes are commercially available and easy

to synthesize and present in large number of biological systems in various important physiological processes. Iron porphyrins which are the mimics of biologically active materials have been extensively studied for epoxidation catalysis. For lower alkenes such as ethylene, propene, butene and hexene heterogeneous epoxidation catalysts are mainly used²⁷⁻²⁹. The authors would like to review the role of iron complexes as homogenous catalysts towards the yield the epoxides of some selected and simple alkenes³⁰⁻⁴⁹.

Catalyzing different substrates:

cis- and *trans*-Stilbene:

Scheme 1. Conversion of stilbene to stilbene oxide.

Some reputed reports have been cited³³⁻³⁷ relating to the conversion of *cis-* and *trans*-stilbene to corresponding oxide (Scheme 1). Different catalysts are giving different % yield of the respective oxide.

cis-Stilbene was epoxidized by (chloro-5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrinato)iron(III) and iodosylbenzene in 77% yield, *trans*-stilbene was unreactive under these conditions³³. This selectivity is remarkable since typical epoxidizing reagents such as peroxyacids have shown to react with *cis*-olefins only about two times faster than the corresponding *trans*-olefins. For *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in methylene chloride at room temperature *cis-* and *trans*-stilbene are epoxidized at equal rates. The reaction of a mixture of *cis-* and *trans*-stilbene with (chloro-5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrinato)iron(III) and iodosylbenzene showed that *cis*-epoxide formed at least 15 times faster than the *trans*-epoxide under these competitive conditions. This selectivity was inferred to result from non-bonded interactions between the phenyl groups of *trans*-stilbene and the pendant phenyl group of the catalyst.

The epoxidation of *cis-* and *trans*-stilbene in the presence of non-porphyrin iron complex [Fe(cyclam)(CF₃SO₃)₂] where cyclam = 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane and hydrogen peroxide as oxidant gave a 26% yield of *cis*-stilbene oxide and 1.7% of *trans*-stilbene oxide³⁴. Formation of epoxides was not detected in the absence of the iron catalyst. Iodosylbenzene instead of hydrogen peroxide as oxidant was also effective in this process. HOO⁻ complex of iron-cyclam was an intermediate of this reaction.

In 2002 W. Nam *et al.*³⁵ have studied an anionic ligand effect in iron porphyrin complex for competitive epoxidations of *cis-* and *trans*-stilbenes. The ratios of *cis-* to *trans*-stilbene oxides obtained in the reactions of [Fe(TPP)X] (TPP = *meso*-tetraphenylporphyrinato dianion and X⁻ = anionic ligand) and iodosylbenzene were 14 and 0.9 when the X⁻ of [Fe(TPP)X] was Cl⁻ and CF₃SO₃⁻, respectively. High ratios of *cis-* to *trans*-stilbene oxides were obtained in the reactions of iron porphyrin catalysts containing anionic ligands such as Cl⁻ and OAc⁻, the ratios of *cis-* to *trans*-stilbene oxide were low in the reactions of iron porphyrin complexes containing non-ligating or weakly-ligating anionic ligands such as SbF₆⁻, CF₃SO₃⁻ and ClO₄⁻. They suggested that the dependence of product ratios on the anionic ligands of iron(III) porphyrin catalysts is due to the involvement of different reactive species in olefin epoxidation reactions. High valent iron(IV) oxoporphyrin cation radicals are generated as a reactive species in the reactions of iron porphyrin catalysts containing non-ligating or weakly-ligating anionic ligands such as SbF₆⁻, CF₃SO₃⁻ and ClO₄⁻ whereas oxidant-iron(III) porphyrin complexes are the reactive intermediates in the reactions of iron porphyrin catalysts containing anionic ligands such as Cl⁻ and OAc⁻.

K. Hasan *et al.* in 2011³⁶ developed a practical and environmentally friendly method of olefin epoxidation by combining FeCl₃·6H₂O and 1-methyl imidazole (as additive) in acetone using hydrogen peroxide as terminal oxidant. They showed the addition of 1-methyl imidazole dramatically enhance the yield of epoxidation of *trans*-stilbene from 40 to 90% under the same conditions.

In 2013 B. Biswas *et al.*³⁷ presented a new dinuclear Fe^{III} complex [Fe₂(μ_{1,3}-O₂Cfn)(OH₂)(MeOH)Cl₂L] in CH₃CN [fn = furan, L1 = N,N'-bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol] which can be used as a suitable epoxidation catalyst of

Table 1. Catalytic epoxidation of *cis*- and *trans*-stilbene by different iron complexes

Entry	Compound	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	<i>cis</i> -Stilbene	FeTPPCI	PhIO	77	33
2	<i>cis</i> -Stilbene	Fe(cyclam)(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	26	34
3	<i>trans</i> -Stilbene	Fe(cyclam)(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	36	34
4	<i>cis</i> -Stilbene	Fe(TPP)Cl	PhIO	56	35
5	<i>trans</i> -Stilbene	Fe(TPP)Cl	PhIO	04	35
6	<i>cis</i> -Stilbene	Fe(TPP)(CF ₃ SO ₃)	PhIO	26	35
7	<i>trans</i> -Stilbene	Fe(TPP)(CF ₃ SO ₃)	PhIO	28	35
8	<i>trans</i> -Stilbene	FeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O in 1-methylimidazole	H ₂ O ₂	90	36
9	<i>trans</i> -Stilbene	FeCl ₂ in 1-methylimidazole	H ₂ O ₂	49	36
10	<i>trans</i> -Stilbene	FeBr ₃ in 1-methylimidazole	H ₂ O ₂	0	36
11	<i>trans</i> -Stilbene	[Fe ₂ (μ _{1,3} -O ₂ Cfn)(OH ₂)(MeOH)Cl ₂ L1]	TBHP	85	37

trans-stilbene. They successfully reported the effect of different oxidants and different solvents towards the epoxidation of *trans*-stilbene. It was shown that TBHP (tert-butyl hydroperoxide) in acetonitrile solvent that iron complex gave 85% *trans*-stilbene oxide whereas under the same condition iodosylbenzene (PhIO) gave 69% corresponding oxide. They also showed the epoxidation of the same compound in dichloromethane solvent gave slightly lower yield i.e. 81% for TBHP and 68% for PhIO using the iron complex as catalyst. They suggested that when PhIO was used as the terminal oxidant the epoxidation proceeded via formation of higher valent iron-oxo species whereas no such species had been detected when TBHP was used as the terminal oxidant. Acetonitrile was observed to be a better choice of solvent and TBHP emerged as the better terminal oxidant in terms of the yield of the epoxidation.

1-Propene:

Scheme 2. Conversion of 1-propene to 1-propene oxide.

1-Propene was epoxidized (Scheme 2) using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant in presence of the catalytic activity of an iron(II) complex coordinated by the tetradentate di(o-imidazol-2-ylidenepyridine)methane ligand (L2), i.e. [Fe(L2)(MeCN)₂](PF₆)₂ gave only 11% of the corresponding epoxide³⁸. In this reaction the major product was 1,2-propane-di-ol.

Table 2. Epoxidation of 1-propene using iron complex as catalyst

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	[Fe(L2)(MeCN) ₂](PF ₆) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	11	38

trans-2-Pentene:

Scheme 3. Conversion of *trans*-2-pentene to *trans*-2-pentene oxide.

Groves and Visky³⁹ prepared compound from αβαβ-tetrakis(2'-aminoyl)porphyrin and 2,2'-dimethoxy-1,1'-bis-6-naphthoylchloride, and the corresponding chloroiron(III) complex known as "Vaulted Binaphthyl" iron-porphyrin complex to catalyze the epoxidation of *trans*-2-pentene using iodosylbenzene as oxidant.

Table 3. Epoxidation of *trans*-2-pentene using iron complex as catalyst

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	Vaulted binaphthyl iron-porphyrin	PhIO	42	39

1-Heptene:

Scheme 4. Conversion of 1-heptene to 1-heptene oxide.

Table 4. Epoxidation of 1-heptene using iron complex as catalyst

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	$[(\text{phen})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_2(\mu\text{-O})(\text{ClO}_4)_4$	CH_3COOOH	88	40

Epoxidation of 1-heptene (Scheme 4) with non-porphyrin complex like $[(\text{phen})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_2(\mu\text{-O})(\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) in presence of peracetic acid as oxidant gave 88% yield of epoxide of 1-heptene in acetonitrile solution⁴⁰. Low loadings of catalyst are sufficient for high conversions. Under identical reaction conditions excluding the iron catalyst, insignificant epoxidation of terminal alkenes is observed. Both the *in situ* catalyst preparation and the epoxidation reaction itself provide significant advantages over other epoxidation procedures for terminal olefins.

cis-2-Heptene:

Scheme 5. Conversion of *cis*-2-heptene to *cis*-2-heptene oxide.

The two non-heme iron complexes $[(\text{BPMEN})\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_2]$ and $[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_2]$ [BPMEN = N,N'-bis-(2-pyridylmethyl)-N,N'-dimethyl-1,2-ethylenediamine; TPA = tris-(2-pyridylmethyl)amine, OTf = CF_3SO_3^-] were the effective catalysts to epoxidize *cis*-2-heptene (Scheme 8) by hydrogen peroxide. The addition of acetic acid inhibited olefin *cis*-hydroxylation and enhances epoxidation for both the catalysts. Optimal conditions were found using a 1:2 mixture of acetonitrile and acetic acid affording epoxide yields of about 90% for both. These excellent yields were improved to nearly 100% by carrying out the reaction at 0°C. Without the use of catalyst negligible autoxidation procedures were obtained⁴¹.

Table 5. Epoxidation of *cis*-2-heptene using iron complexes as catalyst

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	$[(\text{BPMEN})\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_2]$	H_2O_2	77	41
2	$[(\text{TPA})\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_2]$	H_2O_2	44	41

1-Octene:

Scheme 6. Conversion of 1-octene to 1-octene oxide.

The epoxidation of 1-octene in the presence of non-porphyrin iron complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{cyclam})(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2]$ where cyclam = 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane and hydrogen peroxide as oxidant gave 14% of corresponding epoxide³⁴. Formation of epoxide was not detected in the absence of the iron catalyst.

In 2014 J. W. Kück *et al.*³⁸ reported epoxidation of 1-octene with the catalytic activity of an organometallic iron(II) complex coordinated by the tetradentate ligand (L2) i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{L}2)(\text{MeCN})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$ [L2 = di(o-imidazol-2-ylidene)pyridine methane]. In this reaction H_2O_2 was used as oxidant and the yield of epoxide was about 58%.

G. Dubois *et al.* in 2003³⁹ presented an efficient non-porphyrin iron(III) epoxidation catalyst $[(\text{phen})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_2(\mu\text{-O})(\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) to epoxidize 1-octene using peracetic acid (CH_3COOOH) as the oxidant. In this reaction 92% yield was obtained in acetonitrile solution at lower temperature (0°C). This non-porphyrin catalyst was synthesized from inexpensive and commercially available compounds. This system constituted a bioinspired non-heme iron complex capable of competent epoxidation of olefins.

In 2014 T. Chishiro *et al.*⁴² developed an efficiently applicable iron catalyst to epoxidize olefins. The iron complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{pic})(\text{Me-pic})_2]$ [where picH = picolinic acid and Me-picH = 6-methyl-2-picolinic acid] effectively catalyzed 1-octene to its corresponding oxide in 17% yield using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant in acetonitrile solvent. It was hypothesized that Fe^{V} -oxo species would be generated as an active species in the reaction. In this reaction acetonitrile played a critical role in stabilizing the iron(III) and iron(V) species during the reaction.

Table 6. Catalytic epoxidation of 1-octene by different iron complexes

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	[Fe(cyclam)(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂]	H ₂ O ₂	14	34
2	[Fe(L2)(MeCN) ₂](PF ₆) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	58	38
3	[((phen) ₂ (H ₂ O)Fe ^{III}) ₂ (μ-O)](ClO ₄) ₄	CH ₃ COOOH	92	39
4	[Fe(pic)(Me-pic) ₂]	H ₂ O ₂	17	42

1-Decene:**Scheme 7.** Conversion of 1-decene to 1-decene oxide.

The catalytic epoxidation of 1-decene (Scheme 7) by an iron(II) complex bearing an iron(II) complex coordinated by the tetradentate di(*o*-imidazol-2-ylidenepyridine)methane ligand (L2) i.e. [Fe(L2)(MeCN)₂](PF₆)₂ [L2 = di(*o*-imidazol-2-ylidenepyridine)methane] was reported to yield 51% product using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant³⁸. The reaction was carried out in pyridine, acids or other additives were not required in this reaction. In the range from 150 to 300 equivalents of hydrogen peroxide maximum conversions were reached. At higher and lower oxidant concentrations the conversions decreased.

Five-coordinated square-pyramidal non-porphyrin complexes [FeL3](OTf)₂ [L3 = pyridine containing macrocycles bearing an aminopyridyl pendant arm, OTf = CF₃SO₃⁻] efficiently catalyzed to convert 1-decene using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant to its corresponding epoxide in acetonitrile⁴³. Reactions were carried out either in presence or absence of additives under an argon atmosphere at 25°C. Obviously using of additives (like triflic acid) enhanced the yield (32 to 76%) of the product. Additions of non-coordinating acids other than triflic acid (e.g. perchloric acid) were also effective in promoting the catalytic activity of the complexes. In the absence of additives or in the presence of coordinating acids like hydrochloric acid the above iron(II) complexes did not catalyze epoxidation reactions. These results suggested that the high-spin, five-coordinate forms of complexes did not promote epoxidation reactions, whereas their protonated forms were highly catalytically active.

Table 7. Catalytic epoxidation of 1-decene by different iron complexes

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	[Fe(L2)(MeCN) ₂](PF ₆) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	51	38
2	[FeL3](OTf) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	76	43

Cyclohexene:**Scheme 8.** Conversion of cyclohexene to cyclohexene oxide.

For conversion of cyclohexene to cyclohexene oxide (Scheme 8) some selective published works have been reported^{33,34,38,39,44-46}. Different catalysts are giving different % yield of respective oxide. Groves and Nemo in 1983³³ developed the epoxidation of cyclohexene catalyzed by synthetic iron porphyrins. With (chloro-5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrinato) iron(III) (FeTPPCI), cyclohexene oxide was produced in 55% yield in the presence of iodosylbenzene. Yield was based on iodosylbenzene consumed. In a typical reaction solid iodosylbenzene was added to methylene chloride solution in the porphyrin catalyst at room temperature. Higher yields were obtained when the rate of addition of iodosylbenzene was slow and the concentration of cyclohexene was increased. Exposure of the reaction mixtures to air for short periods had a negligible effect on yields. However, longer exposure to air or oxygen caused the initiation of free radical autoxidation process. Tris-(acetylacetonato)iron(III) was found to be ineffective as a catalyst for the epoxidation of cyclohexene with iodosylbenzene. The epoxidizing intermediate in these reactions is an electrophilic porphyrin species. Iodosylbenzene has transferred an oxygen atom to the iron of the porphyrin to form a reactive iron-oxo intermediate.

In 1991 W. Nam *et al.* reported few non-porphyrin iron

complexes to catalyze olefin epoxidation³⁴. They presented the iron complexes of cyclam (1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane) i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{cyclam})(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2]$ for cyclohexene epoxidation by aqueous hydrogen peroxide in acetonitrile or methanol and reported the yield of cyclohexene oxide about 40% based on hydrogen peroxide. Iodosylbenzene (PhIO) was also found to give high yields of epoxide in the iron cyclam catalyzed reaction. The hypothesis was that an HOO^- complex of iron cyclam might be an intermediate of this reaction.

In 2014 J. W. Kück *et al.*³⁸ reported epoxidation of cyclohexene with the catalytic activity of an organometallic iron(II) complex coordinated by the tetradentate ligand (L2) i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{L2})(\text{MeCN})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$ [L2 = di(*o*-imidazol-2-ylidene-pyridine)methane]. Most probably it is the first example of organometallic iron complex with a direct iron-carbon bond to be used as an epoxidation catalyst. In this reaction H_2O_2 was used as oxidant and the yield of epoxide was about 90%.

G. Dubois *et al.* in 2003³⁹ presented an efficient non-porphyrin iron(III) epoxidation catalyst $[\text{((phen)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}^{\text{III}})_2(\mu\text{-O})](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) to epoxidize cyclohexene using peracetic acid (CH_3COOOH) as the oxidant. In this reaction 85% yield was obtained in acetonitrile solution at lower temperature (0°C). This non-porphyrin catalyst was synthesized from inexpensive and commercially available compounds. This system constituted a bioinspired non-heme iron complex capable of efficient epoxidation of olefins.

Y. M. Goh and W. Nam⁴⁴ in 1999 synthesized a series of high valent iron(IV)oxoporphyrin cation radical complexes with the substituents at the *meso* position of the porphyrin ring. These iron(IV) oxoporphyrin radical complexes were formed from the corresponding iron(III) porphyrin complexes with equivalent amount of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid at low temperature. With the help of this cation radical complexes very satisfactory amount of cyclohexene oxide were obtained (upto 98%) either with the presence or absence of hydrogen peroxide and *t*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BuOOH).

In 2002 K. A. Srinivas *et al.*⁴⁵ developed an efficient procedure for catalyst in alkene epoxidation with hydrogen peroxide catalyzed by water soluble iron(III) porphyrins in environmentally benign ionic liquids. The epoxidation of cyclohexene with hydrogen peroxide catalyzed by tetrakis (2',6'-dichloro-3'-sulfonatophenyl)iron(III) $[\text{Cl}_8\text{TPPS}_4\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$ in 1-butyl-3-methylimidazoliumbromide $[\text{Bmim}][\text{Br}]$ under a nitrogen atmosphere in biphasic conditions. The yield of cyclohexene oxide in this process was about 42% based on substrate. The organic phase containing product was separated after the completion of the reaction leaving behind the catalyst immobilized in ionic liquid. The epoxide formation was believed to proceed through an iron-oxo intermediate.

A. Dutta *et al.* in 2016⁴⁶ developed two cheap and environmentally friendly Fe^{III} catalysts $[\text{Fe}(\text{L4})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{L4})_2(\text{NO}_3)] \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$; where HL4 = 2-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)phenol for epoxidation of olefins. Catalytic epoxidation of cyclohexene had been carried out homo-

Table 8. Catalytic epoxidation of cyclohexene by different iron complexes

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	FeTPPCI	PhIO	55	33
2	$\text{Fe}(\text{cyclam})(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3)_2$	H_2O_2	40	34
3	$[\text{Fe}(\text{L2})(\text{MeCN})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$	H_2O_2	90	38
4	$[\text{((phen)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}^{\text{III}})_2(\mu\text{-O})](\text{ClO}_4)_4$	CH_3COOOH	85	39
5	(TMP) ⁺ Fe ^{IV} =O; TMP = <i>meso</i> -tetramesitylporphyrin	Without using oxidant	75	44
6	(TMP) ⁺ Fe ^{IV} =O; TMP = <i>meso</i> -tetramesitylporphyrin	H_2O_2	21	44
7	(TMP) ⁺ Fe ^{IV} =O	$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + t\text{-BOOH}$	17	44
8	(TDCPP) ⁺ Fe ^{IV} =O; TDCPP = <i>meso</i> -tetrakis(2,6-dichlorophenyl)porphyrin	Without using oxidant	98	44
9	(TDCPP) ⁺ Fe ^{IV} =O	H_2O_2	98	44
10	(TDCPP) ⁺ Fe ^{IV} =O	$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + t\text{-BOOH}$	98	44
11	$[\text{Cl}_8\text{TPPS}_4\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$ in $[\text{Bmim}][\text{Br}]$	H_2O_2	42	45
12	$[\text{Fe}(\text{L4})_2(\text{NO}_3)] \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	H_2O_2	61	46
13	$[\text{Fe}(\text{L4})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]$	H_2O_2	21	46

generously by using aqueous hydrogen peroxide in acetonitrile. The yield of epoxides was almost two times for using nitrate containing complex than the acetate containing ones. Both the reactions proceeded through high valent iron-oxo species such as $L_xFe = O$ intermediate. The relatively lower dissociation energy of a nitrate Fe-O bond compared to an acetate Fe-O could lead to easier opening of an H_2O_2 activation site on the iron atom. This could account for the greater yield of nitrate complex in comparison to acetate ones.

Cyclohexenone:

Scheme 9. Conversion of cyclohexenone to cyclohexenone oxide.

Very few articles have been found for epoxidation of cyclohexenone. Epoxidation of cyclohexenone (Scheme 9) with (chloro-5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrinato)iron(III) (FeTPPCI) gave only 8% of cyclohexenone oxide using iodosylbenzene as oxidant³³. On standing with iodosylbenzene alone cyclohexenone produced small amounts of epoxide. The almost unreactivity of cyclohexenone indicated that the epoxidizing in these reactions was an electrophilic porphyrin species.

Non-porphyrin complex $Fe(cyclam)(CF_3SO_3)_2$; cyclam = (1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane) in presence of hydrogen peroxide produced trace amount of cyclohexenone oxide in the solvent mixture acetonitrile and toluene³⁴.

Table 9. Catalytic epoxidation of cyclohexenone by different iron complexes

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	FeTPPCI	PhIO	08	33
2	$Fe(cyclam)(CF_3SO_3)_2$	H_2O_2	Trace	34

Styrene:

Scheme 10. Conversion of styrene to styrene oxide.

For conversion of styrene to corresponding oxide (Scheme 10) a number of published reports have been highlighted. Different catalysts are giving different % yield of the respective oxide.

A non-heme iron(III) complex $[Fe_2(\mu_{1,3}-O_2Cfn)(OH_2)(MeOH)Cl_2L1]$ in CH_3CN [$fn = \text{furan}$, $L1 = N,N'$ -bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol] gave about 80% yield in acetonitrile and dichloromethane solvent for TBHP (tert-butyl hydroperoxide) as oxidant, whereas slightly lower yield when iodosylbenzene (PhIO) was used as oxidant³⁷. But yield was comparatively high in acetonitrile solvent than dichloromethane ones. When PhIO was used as the terminal oxidant the epoxidation proceeded via formation of higher valent iron-oxo species, whereas no such species had been detected when TBHP as the terminal oxidant.

An iron(II) complex bearing an iron(II) complex coordinated by the tetradentate di(o-imidazol-2-ylidene)pyridine) methane ligand (L2) i.e. $[Fe(L2)(MeCN)_2](PF_6)_2$, an organometallic compound with a Fe-C bond using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant gave styrene oxide very low i.e. only 11% yield³⁸. The aromatic olefin styrene was less prone to epoxidation, this suggested that the nucleophilicity of the olefin was an important factor in the epoxidation and the catalyst reacted electrophilically.

T. Chishiro *et al.* in 2014⁴² developed an efficiently applicable iron catalyst to epoxidize various aromatic olefins to give the corresponding epoxide in high yields. The iron complex $[Fe(pic)(Me-pic)_2]$ [where $picH = \text{picolinic acid}$ and $Me-picH = 6\text{-methyl-2-picolinic acid}$] effectively catalyzed styrene to its corresponding oxide in 93% yield using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant in acetonitrile solvent. It was hypothesized that Fe^V -oxo species would be generated as an active species in the reaction. In this reaction acetonitrile played a critical role in stabilizing the iron(III) and iron(V) species during the reaction.

An efficient epoxidation catalyst $[Cl_8TPPS_4Fe^{III}]$ (where $Cl_8TPPS_4 = \text{tetrakis}(2',6'\text{-dichloro-3'-sulfonatophenyl})\text{porphyrinato ion}$) immobilized in 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide gave 74% yield of styrene oxide using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant⁴⁵. The catalytic activity of catalyst immobilized in ionic liquid in alkene epoxidation was comparable to the activity obtained when the same catalyst was supported on other heterogeneous systems. The epoxide

yields were very low in homogeneous solution (17% yield of styrene oxide). The activity of the catalyst in ionic liquid was shown to be greater than that in conventional solvents.

With the help of non-porphyrin iron(III) catalysts $[\text{Fe}(\text{L}4)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{L}4)_2(\text{NO}_3)]$, $2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ where HL4 = 2-(1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-2-yl)phenol produced different percent of styrene oxide using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant⁴⁶. The nitrate complex gave almost two times greater yield than that of the acetate complex. It was suggested that the Fe-O nitrate bond has lower bond dissociation energy than the corresponding Fe-O acetate bond.

Epoxidation of olefins catalyzed by synthetic iron porphyrin complex was described by Groves and Meyers in 1983⁴⁷. The $5\alpha, 10\beta, 15\alpha, 20\beta$ -tetrakis(*o*-(*R*)-hydratropamidophenyl)porphyrin $\{\text{H}_2\text{T}(\alpha, \beta, \alpha, \beta\text{-Hyd})\text{PP}\}$ and $5\alpha, 10\beta, 15\alpha, 20\beta$ -tetrakis(*o*-[(*S*)-22'-carboxymethyl-1,12'-binaphthyl-2-carboxamido]phenyl)porphyrin $\{\text{H}_2\text{T}(\alpha, \beta, \alpha, \beta\text{-Binap})\text{PP}\}$ iron complexes produced styrene oxide from styrene about 70% yield in the presence of either iodosylbenzene or iodosylmesitylene as the oxygen donors. These reactions involved the initial formation of reactive iron-oxo intermediate from iron porphyrin complex and iodosylbenzene.

H.-L. Yeung *et al.* in 2008⁴⁸ developed a non-heme iron(II) catalyst based on a hexapyridine ligand containing pinene groups attached at two pyridine rings (SPP ligand), which in combination with two equivalents of FeCl_2 provided the diiron complex $[\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}(\mu\text{-O})(\text{Cl})_4(\text{SPP})]$. The complex catalyzed epoxidation of styrenes with hydrogen peroxide as oxidant in presence of acetic acid giving 95% yield in acetonitrile solution at 0°C. When peracetic acid was used as the oxidant, no epoxide product was obtained.

Table 10. Catalytic epoxidation of styrene using iron complexes

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	$[\text{Fe}_2(\mu_{1,3}\text{-O}_2\text{Cfn})(\text{OH})_2(\text{MeOH})\text{Cl}_2\text{L}1]$	TBHP	82	37
2	$[\text{Fe}(\text{L}2)(\text{MeCN})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$	H_2O_2	11	38
3	$[\text{Fe}(\text{pic})(\text{Me-pic})_2]$	H_2O_2	92	42
4	$[\text{Cl}_8\text{TPPS}_4\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$	H_2O_2	74	45
5	$[\text{Fe}(\text{L}4)_2(\text{NO}_3)] \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	H_2O_2	66	46
6	$[\text{Fe}(\text{L}4)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]$	H_2O_2	29	46
7	$\text{Fe}\{\text{H}_2\text{T}(\alpha, \beta, \alpha, \beta\text{-Hyd})\text{PP}\}$	PhIO	65	47
8	$\text{Fe}\{\text{H}_2\text{T}(\alpha, \beta, \alpha, \beta\text{-Binap})\text{PP}\}$	PhIO	67	47
9	$[\text{Fe}_2^{\text{III}}(\mu\text{-O})\text{Cl}_4(\text{SPP})]$	H_2O_2	95	48

Cyclooctene:

Scheme 11. Conversion of cyclooctene to cyclooctene oxide.

Several distinguished research articles showing the conversion of cyclooctene to corresponding oxide (Scheme 11) have been consulted here. Different catalysts are giving different % yield of the respective oxide.

An effective synthetic iron porphyrin catalyst FeTPPCI where TPPCI = (chloro-5,10,15,20-tetra-*o*-tolylporphyrinato) iron(III) produced 84% yield of cyclooctene oxide from cyclooctene using iodosylbenzene as oxidant³³. It was concluded that iodosylbenzene had transferred an oxygen atom to the iron of the porphyrin to form a reactive iron-oxo intermediate.

The catalytic epoxidation of olefins by an organometallic iron(II) complex coordinated by the tetradentate ligand (L2) i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{L}2)(\text{MeCN})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2$ [L2 = di(*o*-imidazol-2-ylidene-pyridine)methane] was investigated³⁸. This catalyst system in presence of hydrogen peroxide as oxidant gave very good epoxide yield i.e. 92% of cyclooctene oxide. It was found that the epoxide yield strongly depended on the amount of the peroxide used and noticeably increased at lower temperatures. This catalyst was stable towards air and water which was a remarkable good candidate for epoxidation reactions. Changing the concentration of hydrogen peroxide showed that the oxidation agent was only the limiting reagent if used in lower amounts, whereas a large excess amount of the oxidant decomposition of the catalyst.

An efficient epoxidation catalyst such as $[\text{((phen)}_2\text{-}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}^{\text{III}})_2(\mu\text{-O})](\text{ClO}_4)_4$ [phen = 1,10-phenanthroline] using peracetic acid as oxidant in presence of acetonitrile solvent was used to give 90% yield of cyclooctene oxide⁴⁰. It was depicted that the sensitivity of epoxidation reaction not only depended on the catalyst but to the reaction conditions as well.

R. Mas-Balleste and L. Que (Jr.) in 2007⁴¹ investigated the chemistry of two non-heme iron complexes

[(BPMEN)Fe(OTf)₂] and [(TPA)Fe(OTf)₂] [BPMEN = N,N'-bis-(2-pyridylmethyl)-N,N'-dimethyl-1,2-ethylenediamine; TPA = tris-(2-pyridylmethyl)amine; OTf = triflate ion] those were effective as epoxidation catalysts using hydrogen peroxide as oxidant in acetonitrile-acetic acid solvent mixture. The addition of acetic acid enhanced the epoxidation activity of the catalysts. Reactions carried out at 0°C with 0.5 mol% catalyst and a 1:1.5 olefin/H₂O₂ mol ratio in a 1:2 CH₃CN/CH₃COOH solvent mixture resulted in nearly quantitative conversions of cyclooctene to corresponding oxide within 1 min. It was proposed the most likely epoxidizing agent to be [(L')Fe^V(O)(OOCCH₃)₂]²⁺ where L' = BPMEN/TPA.

S. Taktak *et al.* in 2007⁴³ developed a novel iron(II) complex with pentadentate aminopyridyl pyridine ligands (L3) was found to catalyze cyclooctene epoxidation in the presence of triflate (CF₃SO₃⁻ or OTf⁻) anion. Here hydrogen peroxide was used as oxidant in acetonitrile solvent and the yield of cyclohexene oxide was about 90%. Additions of non-coordinating acids other than triflic acid such as perchloric acid were also effective in promoting the catalytic activity of the complex. Smaller amounts of triflic acid still enhanced the catalytic properties of these systems also to a lesser extent. It was suggested that the high-spin, five-coordinate forms of the complex did not promote epoxidation reactions, whereas their promoted form was highly catalytically active.

The catalyst [Cl₈TPPS₄Fe^{III}] (where Cl₈TPPS₄ = tetrakis(2',6'-dichloro-3'-sulfonatophenyl)porphyrinato ion) in presence of 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide (an ionic liquid) as solvent and hydrogen peroxide as oxidant gave greater yield (81% cyclooctene oxide) in comparison to other conventional solvents⁴⁵. The organic phase containing product was separated after the completion of the reaction leaving behind the catalyst immobilized in ionic liquid. The epoxide formation was believed to proceed through an iron-oxo intermediate.

Y. Feng *et al.* in 2011⁴⁹ developed macrocyclic non-heme iron complex Fe(Me₂EBC)(OTf)₂; where Me₂EBC = 4,11-dimethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazabicyclo [6.6.2]hexadecane and OTf = CF₃SO₃⁻ effective for catalyzing olefin epoxidation. The complex has tetraazamacrocyclic ligand based on cyclam. In this reaction acetic acid as additive was used in presence of H₂O₂ as oxidant giving satisfactory yield of epoxide.

Table 11. Catalytic epoxidation of cyclooctene by different iron complexes

Entry	Catalyst	Oxidant	Yield (%)	Reference
1	FeTTPCI	PhIO	84	33
2	[Fe(L2)(MeCN) ₂](PF ₆) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	92	38
3	[((phen) ₂ (H ₂ O)Fe ^{III}) ₂ (μ-O)](ClO ₄) ₄	CH ₃ COOOH	90	40
4	Fe(BPMEN)(OTf) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	99	41
5	[(TPA)Fe(OTf) ₂]	H ₂ O ₂	98	41
6	[FeL3](OTf) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	89	43
7	[Cl ₈ TPPS ₄ Fe ^{III}]	H ₂ O ₂	81	45
8	Fe(Me ₂ EBC)(OTf) ₂	H ₂ O ₂	67	49

Conclusion

Groves' first report dealing with the catalytic epoxidation of olefins by synthetic iron-porphyrins has actively motivated explosive growth of iron based coordination compounds of both porphyrins and non-porphyrins for catalytic epoxidation of alkenes. Although a good number of non-porphyrin iron complexes have been developed for this purpose, porphyrin based catalysts dominated the field. Synthetic iron porphyrin complexes gave higher yield of epoxide for electron-rich olefins in comparison to electron-deficient ones. Epoxidation of 1-propene is still a challenge to get good yield. Epoxidation of ethylene, butene and hexane with homogeneous iron catalysis is rarely reported. Most of the reactions approached through iron-oxo intermediates. Considerable advancement have been made regarding both porphyrin and non-porphyrin iron complexes but there is a greater demand to device the suitable experimental parameters (solvent, additive, temperature, reaction time and others) to improve efficiency. Uses of ionic liquids instead of normal conventional solvents are highly appreciated. Iron complexes are undoubtedly cheaper and eco-friendly in comparison to other celebrated noble metal based epoxidation catalysts. In many cases iodosylbenzene is used as a source of oxygen but it is not environmentally friendly. There is greater need to develop alternative eco-friendly oxidants. Preferably atmospheric oxygen and even hydrogen peroxide could be the alternative source of oxygen for epoxidation of olefins catalyzed by iron complexes.

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